

Analysis the Influence of Full Day School on the Motivation to Learn in Madrasah Aliyah

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ABSTRACT

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This study aims to investigate the effect of the implementation of the Full Day School system on the learning motivation of Aqidah Akhlak class XI students at MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek during the 2024/2025 academic year. The research method used is ex facto research. Ex-post facto research examines cause-and-effect relationships that are not manipulated or not treated by researchers. The research sample consists of two groups, namely Group 1, namely Class XI IPA 1 and Group 2, namely Class XI IPA 2 which follows Full Day School. Data were collected through a questionnaire that measured the level of student learning motivation in Aqidah Akhlak lessons after the implementation of Full Day School. Data analysis was conducted using statistical techniques. The results showed that there was a significant difference in Aqidah Akhlak learning motivation between Group 1, namely Class XI IPA 1 and Group 2, namely Class XI IPA 2 after the implementation of full day school. It can be seen from the significance level value of $0.023 < 0.05$, meaning that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. It can also be seen from the comparison of r count with r table, namely $2.497 > 0.444$, meaning H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. Based on the results of the data processing above, the Mean Different value is 9,600, the value is positive, meaning that the influence arising from full day school on learning motivation is positive.

KEYWORDS:

Full Day School, Learning Motivation

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a must for a society that has a state, the government also continues to update educational programs so that in the future they are more qualified and can help the community. (Arisanti & Sauri, 2022) Education plays an important role in improving human resources (HR), quality education will be obtained in quality schools. While quality schools will produce quality human resources as well. Apart from that, humans must also understand the importance of learning. That learning is a discovery that is in accordance with the active search for humans, and in itself gives the best results. Make your own efforts to find solutions and produce knowledge that is truly meaningful. (Jaguna, 2023) In the field of education, the learning process is the main focus of learning. (Budiyono, 2020) This is because the learning

process is the main indicator in efforts to improve student achievement. A good learning process will certainly produce good results too. (Prasetya, 2021)

However, the reality on the ground shows that various educational challenges such as declining learning quality, lack of post-school supervision, and increasing global competition, have created the need for a more comprehensive approach to education. Students often face limited time for deepening material, while dependence on gadgets and social media diverts their focus from productive learning activities. The achievement gap between students from different socio-economic backgrounds is widening, partly due to differences in access to additional educational resources. Traditional education systems also often fail to adequately prepare students for higher education and the world of work, with an excessive focus on exams and neglect of developing essential life skills. Social and behavioral problems among adolescents, such as delinquency and bullying, are increasing due to a lack of purposeful activities after school hours. (Dewantara, 2024)

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The implementation of the full day school system on student learning motivation is designed as a comprehensive solution to improve the quality of education. The system offers longer learning time, allowing the use of more diverse and interactive teaching methods, as well as more intensive character and soft skills development. A conducive and controlled learning environment, supported by the integration of modern technology and resources, creates an atmosphere that encourages student focus and engagement. A holistic approach to education, encompassing academic, social, emotional and physical aspects, is the foundation for motivating the whole student. A balanced curriculum of academic lessons, extracurricular activities and breaks, supported by adequate facilities and specially trained teaching staff, ensures an optimal learning experience. Flexibility in learning and continuous evaluation ensure the system can adapt to the individual needs of students and the changing demands of education. (Dewantara, 2024)

Full day school is an effort to maximize and develop the potential of students who balance between hard skills and soft skills, and their personality or character still causes problems. (Asmuni, 2024) For example, most people are still against the implementation of full day school, which is considered to be too burdensome on the cognitive aspect and too burdensome for students with long learning time. Students who are part of the community have different perceptions of each individual. Some students feel that this system is very time-consuming, usually they can spend time playing or doing things they like, but now they have to spend it studying at school. (Muti'ah & Sholeh, 2020)

The full day school system is not a new system in the world of education in Indonesia. This educational concept has been around for a long time, namely in Islamic boarding schools. Generally, students study full day even until late at night to study Islamic religion (Al-Qur'an and Hadith) and other general knowledge. This education is patterned on boarding school education. This can trigger students' own motivation in participating in learning because students and female students feel more excited when the learning process is carried out together. Even though the conditions are quite tiring because of the increased learning time and duration. (Bahrani, 2021)

Learning motivation plays a crucial role in education as a key driver of student achievement. It is the internal force that drives, directs and sustains learning behavior. Motivation stems from various factors, both internal and external, which include psychological drives, personal needs, and environmental influences. (Azhar, 2020) However, student motivation is not the only factor determining the success of learning. Teacher competence in applying effective learning strategies, methods and models is also very important. A skilled educator can create a supportive learning environment, stimulate curiosity and facilitate deep understanding. (Ikhtiarini & Ratnaningrum, 2024) The combination of strong student motivation and teacher

pedagogical expertise creates a synergy that promotes optimal academic achievement. This holistic approach not only improves learning achievement, but also develops critical thinking skills, creativity and problem-solving abilities that are essential for students' future success. (Hapudin, 2021)

Several studies have shown that students benefit academically and socially from full day school. The length of learning time is also one of the dimensions of children's experience. Full day school besides aiming to develop the quality of education, the most important thing is that full day school aims as one of the efforts to increase student learning motivation. Good student learning motivation can be observed from the attendance of students who apply full day school which is increasing day by day. This proves that the application of the full day school system has something to do with student learning motivation in participating in the learning activity process.

Research conducted by Nugroho Hadi Utomo and Dr. Heru Totok Tri Wahono M.Pd entitled The Influence of Fullday School System on Student Learning Motivation of Social Studies Department (case study at SMA Negeri Kabuh Jombang) in the results of the analysis shows that there is an influence of fullday school on student learning motivation of Social Studies Department of SMA Negeri Kabuh, Jombang. The tcount value is 7.567, sig value is 0.00 <0.05, and regression coefficient is 1.435. There is a positive influence of fullday school on the learning motivation of social studies students of SMA Negeri Kabuh, Jombang. (STKIP, 2022)

Second, in a study conducted by Gusti Ayu Nyoman Dyah Malini and I Gusti Ayu Diah Fridari entitled Differences in student learning motivation in terms of gender and birth order at SMAN 1 Tabanan with a full day school system, based on the results of research conducted obtained a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) meaning that there are differences in motivation when viewed from gender. In addition, in terms of birth order, the results of the study obtained a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) meaning that there are differences in motivation when viewed from birth order. Seeing this, there are differences in student learning motivation in terms of gender and birth order at SMA N 1 Tabanan with a full day school system. (Malini & Fridari, 2019)

Third, research conducted by Desi Amanda, Abdul Wahab and St. Johariyah in their research entitled The Effect of Fullday School on Student Motivation shows that from the results of the research the implementation of fullday school at SMAN 18 Makassar is going well with learning activities and other activities but cannot be separated from other factors that also influence its implementation. The data from the analysis of the instrument question with hypothesis test (t-test) then obtained the value of t count 3.309 \bar{E} t table 1.998 with the significance of the effect of X1 on Y of 0.002 \bar{E} 0.05 which means H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected and it can be concluded that there is an effect of X1 on Y and based on the

value of t count in the table which is 2.758 $\bar{E}f$ t table with a significance level of 0.007 \bar{E} 0.05 then H_a is accepted and rejects H_o so it can be concluded that the variable X_2 has an effect on Y . with the results of the hypothesis there is a significant influence on Y . with the results of the hypothesis that there is a significant effect of full day school on student learning motivation at SMAN 18 Makassar with the duration of study (X_1) by 13.3% and the condition of students (X_2) by 9.50% and the remaining 77.2% is influenced by other variables not included in this study. (Amanda, D., Wahab, A., & Johariyah, 2023)

The research on "The Effect of Full Day School on Aqidah Akhlak Learning Motivation of Class XI MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 2024/2025 Academic Year" offers a new perspective in educational studies by integrating several aspects that have not been widely explored before. The novelty of this research lies in its specific focus on the subject of Aqidah Akhlak in the context of the full day school system, a relatively new educational approach in many countries. The study is unique in that it combines elements of traditional religious education with modern learning models, allowing for an in-depth exploration of how extended learning time affects students' motivation in learning and internalizing religious values. Furthermore, this study has the potential to reveal new insights into the effectiveness of religious teaching in a full-day school setting, as well as the possibility of synergy or conflict between the academic demands of full day school and the need for reflection and appreciation in the learning of Aqidah Akhlak. With its relevance to current education policy, this study not only contributes to the academic literature, but can also provide valuable input for policy makers in designing an education system that accommodates academic and spiritual needs in a balanced manner. This novelty makes the study an important step in understanding the dynamics of learning motivation in the modern education era, particularly in the context of religious subjects.

Based on the results of pre-research observations that have been carried out at the research location at MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek. Researchers found an overview of the implementation of the Full Day School system at MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek during the 2024/2025 academic year. The learning methods used are very good accompanied by syllabuses and lesson plans that are in accordance with the K13 curriculum, teacher-student interactions are fairly good. This is because student interaction is not only in class but also outside the classroom. and the facilities available are adequate so that they support the learning process to be more effective. Then the enthusiasm of students is so high in participating in full day school learning even though there are some students who sleep in the ongoing learning.

1. Full day school

a. Definition of Full day school

The word full day school comes from English, full means full, day means day, and school means

school. Full day school means a school that is conducted throughout the day or the learning process is carried out from morning to evening. (Wicaksono, 2018). This school allocates more time compared to the learning process in schools that do not implement the full day school programme. So, schools are more free to organise the lesson hours which are adjusted to the weight of the lesson and added to the deepening model. The full day school system in Indonesia began with the proliferation of the term superior around the 1990s which was widely developed by private schools. The full day school system in Indonesia began with the proliferation of the term superior around the 1990s which was widely developed by private schools, including schools labelled as Islamic. (Alimni & Faaris, 2019). Ideally, an excellent school is a school that focuses on the quality of the learning process, not the quality of student input, including schools labelled as Islamic. Ideally, an excellent school is one that focuses on the quality of the learning process, not the quality of student input. (Hairunnisa, 2019).

In addition to developing quality management in education, the main purpose of full day school is to improve students' faith and morals and instil positive values. Full day schools also provide a strong foundation for learning in all aspects, namely intellectual, physical, social and emotional development. (Budiman, 2017).

b. Advantages and disadvantages of full day school

Advantages and disadvantages of full day school Every education system has advantages and disadvantages. The advantages and disadvantages of the full day school system are as follows:

1) The advantages of full day school are as a progressive breakthrough in the world of education, full day school is in great demand by parents with high mobility or parents who are aware of the challenges of an increasingly difficult era where the role of parents is no longer dominant in children's education. (Yuspawati, 2019). The attractions of full day school include optimising the use of time, exploring and developing talents intensively, teaching the importance of process, focusing on learning, maximising potential. (Khurotunisa, 2021). Expertise in designing full day school so that it is not boring. The full day school system requires attention and seriousness of management for managers, so that the learning process in educational institutions that are patterned full day school takes place optimally, it requires attention and an outpouring of thought especially from the management, even sacrifices both physical, psychological, material and others. Without this, full day school will not achieve

optimal results and may even be just a meaningless routine. (Setyawan et al., 2021).

- 2) The weakness of full day school is that the full day school system often causes boredom in students. The learning system with a full day school pattern requires good physical, psychological, and intellectual readiness to develop creativity and children are better controlled. (Siregar, 2017).

The dense planning of learning activities and the consistent application of sanctions will to some extent cause students to become bored. However, for those who are prepared, this is not a problem, but will bring its own worries, therefore, management foresight and improvisation are needed in this regard. (Ma'murasmi, 2017).

Expertise in designing full day schools so that they are not boring. The full day system demands attention and seriousness from the manager, so that the learning process in educational institutions with full day patterns becomes optimal, demanding a lot of attention and outpouring, especially from the manager, but also physically, psychologically, materially and other sacrifices. (Hikma, 2020). Without this, full day school will not achieve optimal results, and may even become a useless routine.

2. Learning Motivation

Motivation to learn is the overall driving force both within (internal) and outside (external) that ensures continuity and gives direction to learning activities, so that the desired or desired goals of students are achieved. (Suratman et al., 2019). Motivation is also an activity that puts a person or a group that has certain and personal needs, to work to complete their tasks. Motivation is also defined as a driver or activator that conditions individuals and is then directed to achieve a goal. Someone will only want to learn if there is a willingness to learn. (Oci, 2019).

Motivation is needed in teaching activities, because motivation encourages enthusiasm for learning and vice versa, lack of motivation will weaken the spirit of learning. Motivation is an absolute requirement in learning. A student who has no motivation to learn (lack of motivation) will not succeed optimally. (Supriani et al., 2020).

The position of motivation lies with the teacher who always motivates his students in learning. For this reason, the emergence of motivation in students is influenced by teachers who arouse their motivation so that learning becomes more enthusiastic. Therefore, both intrinsic (internal) and extrinsic (external) motivation must exist in students so that the learning objectives that have been formulated can be achieved optimally. (Amalia & Maknun, 2021).

METHODS

This research uses ex-post facto research. Ex-post facto research is one of the various types of research, both natural science and social science research. The term ex-post facto indicates that changes in the independent variable have occurred, the researcher is faced with the problem of how to determine the cause of the effect being observed. (Syahrizal & Jailani, 2023) Ex-post facto research examines cause-and-effect relationships that are not manipulated or not given treatment by researchers. Cause-and-effect research is conducted on programs, activities or events that have taken place or have occurred. The existence of a cause-and-effect relationship is based on theoretical studies, that a variable is caused or backgrounded by certain variables or causes certain variables. (Aliefian, 2021)

The data collection technique used in this study is a non-test technique in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire technique is a technique used in data collection by giving a questionnaire to respondents who have been arranged with a number of questions and statements with answer options that have been provided. Answer choices in objective types such as true/false. (Zainal, 2020)

This technique will be efficient when viewed from the variables to be measured and can see what is expected of respondents. Such as the type and form of the question, and does not lead to only one answer and the questions written should not be too long, which is important to be understood and understood by the respondent. Then the data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive parametric analysis technique. Descriptive data analysis is an analysis that is used with the aim of only describing data. Descriptive data analysis is also called univariate analysis. Descriptive research data testing to find the frequency value, mean (average), mode, median and standard deviation. (Handayani, 2023) After that, researchers must carry out the prerequisite analysis test, namely the normality test and the hegemony test before conducting the hypothesis test to find out whether there is an influence between Full day school on student learning motivation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Result

1. Data Description

The results of the study explained in detail about the effect of full day school on motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak for students of class XI MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 2024/2025 academic year. Based on this research using ex-post facto research. Ex-post facto research is one of the various types of research, both natural science and social science research. The term ex-post facto indicates that changes in the independent variable have occurred, the researcher is faced with the problem of how to determine the cause of the effect being observed. Ex-post facto research examines cause-and-effect

relationships that are not manipulated or not given treatment by researchers. Cause-and-effect research is conducted on programs, activities or events that have taken place or have occurred. The existence of a cause-and-effect relationship is based on theoretical studies, that a variable is caused or backgrounded by certain variables or causes certain variables. In order to make it easier to provide treatment to group 1, namely class XI IPA 1 and group 2, namely class XI IPA 2. In this study, researchers only used two classes XI IPA 1 and XI IPA 2 totaling 20 students, each class consisting of 10 students.

a. Research Instrument Results

To find out the Effect of Full day school on Motivation to Learn Aqidah Akhlak Sisiwa class XI MA Al- Khairiyah NW Rajek Lesson Year 2024/2025. Researchers use instruments, which are tools used by researchers to collect data by making measurements. The instrument used in this research is a questionnaire. The assessment in this questionnaire instrument is to use a Likert scale, namely the assessment is 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. For the SS answer, the point is 5, then, S point is 4, KS point is 3, TS point is 2 and STS point is 1.

b. Science 1 and Science 2 Class Test Results

Based on the results of research that has been conducted using a questionnaire, the following data is obtained. It can be seen that student motivation is higher after the implementation of Full day school. The following are the results of this study:

Table 4.1. Results of Questionnaire Research in Science 1 and Science 2 Classes

NO	Student Name XI IPA 1	Value	Student Name XI IPA 2	Value
1.	Arifin	63	M. Zainuddin	85
2.	Egi Ispani	75	Nisa Sulistia	62
3.	Fauzan Efendi	61	Rahim Saputra	81
4.	Gea Yunanda	66	Rohmi Hidayati	93
5.	Kamaludin	79	Sabil Ahmad	74
6.	Leni Fitriani	61	Tuti Indiani	84
7.	Leni Zamayani	71	Zohara	79
8.	Misnah	77	Ria Apriani	69
9.	Muh. Khaerul A.	68	Yusril	66
10.	M. Khaenudin	57	Hairil Nizam	81

2. Analysis Requirement Test

Before testing the hypothesis, researchers are required to test the normality and hegemony of the data. Because here the researcher wants to find whether there is an effect of full day school on the motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak Sisiwa class XI Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 2024/2025 school year. So the data used by researchers in testing the requirements of analysis and hypotheses is questionnaire data. The questionnaire data shows data after treatment using Full day school. The following are the results of the analysis requirements test:

1) Normality Test Results with the Help of SPSS 24.0

The normality test result is a test carried out with the aim of assessing the distribution of data in a group of data or variables, whether the data distribution is normally distributed or not. (Fahmeyzan et al., 2018) The results of the normality test can be seen in the table below:

Table 4.2 Normality Test Results

Tests of Normality					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df
motivasi	,102	20	,200*	,968	20
*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.					
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction					

Decision making basis

- 1) If the Kolmogorov-Smirov sig value > 0.05 then the value is normally distributed.
- 2) If the Kolmogorov-Smirov sig value < 0.05 then the data is not normally distributed.

Based on the results of the normality test above, we can see the significance level value. Kolmogorov-Smirov 0.200 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

2) Homogeneity Test Results with the Help of SPSS 24.0

The results of the homogeneity test with the help of SPSS 24.0 serve to determine whether the data is homogeneous or not. As in the following table.

Table 4.3 Results of homogeneity test

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

Motivasi			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
,595	1	18	,451

- 1) If the significance value > 0.05 then the data distribution is homogeneous
- 2) If the significance value <0.05, then the data distribution is not homogeneous

Based on the homogeneity test results above, it can be seen that the sig value is 0.451 > 0.05, so the data is homogeneous.

3. Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis testing can be done through independent t test, carried out to test whether there is an effect of full day school on motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak for students of class XI MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 2024/2025 academic year.'

Table 4.4: Hypothetical Test Results

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
motivation	Equal variances assumed	,595	,451	2,97	18	,022	9,600	3,844	1,524	17,676
	Equal variances not assumed			2,97	17,45	,023	9,600	3,844	1,491	17,709

The test step is as follows:

Determining H0 and Ha

H0= There is no effect of full day school on motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak for students of class XI MA Al- Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 202/2025 academic year.

Ha= There is an Influence of Full day school on the Motivation to Learn Aqidah Akhlak for

Students of Class XI MA Al- Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 202/2025 Study Year.

Basis for Decision

a. Based on Significance Level

Determining the significance level. The significance level used is 0.05 (5%).

- 1) If the significance value (2-tailed) <0.05, then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.
- 2) If the significance value (2-tailed) > 0.05, then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected.

b. Based on t table and t count

- 1) If t count ≤ t table then H0 accepted (Ha rejected)
- 2) If t count > t table then Ha is accepted (H0 is rejected)

Decision making

a. Based on the significance level

The value of the significance level (2-tailed) is 0.023 <0.05, meaning that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, namely that there is an effect of full day school on the motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak for students in class XI MA Al- Khairiyah NW Rajek in the 202/2025 school year.

b. Based on t table and t count

The calculated t value obtained is 2.497 > 0.444, meaning that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, namely there is. The Effect of Full day school on Motivation to Learn Aqidah Akhlak Student class XI MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek Lesson Year 2024/2025.

B. Discouisioun

In the academic year 2024/2025, a groundbreaking study was conducted at MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek, a school that had recently implemented a full day system. The researchers, intrigued by the potential impacts of this new schedule, set out to investigate how it affected students' motivation to learn Aqidah Akhlak, a crucial subject in Islamic education that encompasses theology and ethics. This study was not just a matter of academic interest; it held real-world implications for educational policy and the future of religious instruction in Islamic schools. The researchers chose an ex-post facto design for their study, a method that allows for the examination of cause-and-effect relationships in situations where the independent variable - in this case, the full day school system - has already been implemented and cannot be manipulated. This approach, while not as controlled as experimental designs, offers valuable insights into real-world educational scenarios.

The study focused on two groups of students: Class XI IPA 1 and Class XI IPA 2, each comprising 10 students. While the sample size was relatively small, it provided a manageable scope for an in-depth analysis. The researchers were mindful of this limitation, acknowledging that it might affect the generalizability of

their findings to larger populations or different contexts. To measure student motivation, the researchers employed a carefully crafted questionnaire using a Likert scale. This scale ranged from 1 to 5, with 5 representing strong agreement (SS) and 1 representing strong disagreement (STS). This nuanced approach allowed for a quantitative analysis of students' attitudes and perceptions regarding their learning motivation, capturing subtle differences that might not be apparent through more simplistic measures.

After collecting the questionnaire data, the researchers embarked on a rigorous process of statistical analysis. They began with tests for normality and homogeneity, crucial steps in ensuring the validity of their subsequent analyses. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality yielded a significance value of 0.200, comfortably above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that the data was normally distributed. Similarly, Levene's test for homogeneity of variances produced a significance value of 0.451, again above 0.05, suggesting that the variances between the two groups were not significantly different. These results were reassuring, confirming that the data met the necessary assumptions for parametric statistical analysis.

With these preliminary tests completed, the researchers moved on to the crux of their study: hypothesis testing. They employed an independent t-test, a powerful statistical tool for comparing the means of two independent groups. The results were striking. The t-test yielded a t-value of 2.497, with 18 degrees of freedom. Most importantly, the significance level (p-value) was 0.022, falling below the predetermined alpha level of 0.05. This finding led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, providing strong evidence of a statistically significant difference in learning motivation between the two groups.

The mean difference of 9.600 between the groups further underscored the magnitude of this effect. Students in the full day school system showed markedly higher motivation scores compared to their counterparts. This finding is particularly intriguing as it suggests that the extended school hours might be offering more than just additional time for instruction. It hints at the possibility that the full day system creates an environment more conducive to engagement and deeper learning, especially in a subject as nuanced and potentially challenging as Aqidah Akhlak. However, the researchers were careful not to overstate their findings. They acknowledged several limitations of their study. The small sample size of just 20 students, while allowing for detailed analysis, limits the generalizability of the results. The focus on a single subject (Aqidah Akhlak) in one specific school context also raises questions about whether similar effects would be observed in other subjects or different educational settings. Furthermore, while the study demonstrated a correlation between full day schooling and

increased motivation, it did not explore the specific mechanisms by which this increase occurs. These limitations, far from diminishing the value of the study, serve as signposts for future research directions.

The implications of this study are far-reaching. For educators and policymakers in Islamic schools, it suggests that implementing a full day system could be a valuable tool for enhancing student motivation, particularly in subjects that form the core of Islamic education. However, it also underscores the need for more comprehensive research to fully understand the potential benefits and challenges of such a system.

The study opens up several avenues for future investigation. Researchers might explore whether these motivational benefits extend to other subjects beyond Aqidah Akhlak, how they might vary across different grade levels, or whether they persist over longer periods. There's also a pressing need to delve into the specific aspects of full day schooling that contribute to increased motivation. Is it the extended time for reflection and discussion? The opportunity for more varied teaching methods? Or perhaps the creation of a more immersive learning environment? Additionally, future studies could examine any potential drawbacks or challenges associated with the full day school system, ensuring a balanced understanding of its impacts. In conclusion, this research provides a valuable starting point for understanding the relationship between school schedule structures and student motivation in religious education contexts. It highlights the potential of full day schooling to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in subjects like Aqidah Akhlak. However, it also serves as a call to action for more extensive research in this area.

As education systems continue to evolve, particularly in the wake of global changes and challenges, such research will be crucial in shaping policies and practices that best support student learning and engagement. The study from MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek, while focused on a specific context, contributes to a broader conversation about the future of education, the role of religious instruction in schools, and the most effective ways to motivate and engage students in their learning journey. For educators, researchers, and policymakers alike, this study serves as a stepping stone, inviting deeper exploration into the complex interplay between school structures, teaching methodologies, and student motivation. As we move forward, it will be essential to build upon these findings, conducting larger-scale studies across diverse contexts to develop a more comprehensive understanding of how educational systems can best serve the needs of students, particularly in the realm of religious education,

The journey to understanding the full impact of full day schooling on student motivation is just beginning. This study from MA Al-Khairiyah NW Rajek has

illuminated a path forward, sparking questions and inspiring further inquiry. As we continue to explore these questions, we move closer to creating educational environments that truly nurture students' intellectual and spiritual growth, preparing them not just for academic success, but for life-long learning and engagement with their faith and the world around them.

CONCLUSION

The type of research used in this study is ex facto which is carried out in two classes, namely in XI IPA 1 and XI IPA 2. For IPA 1 class using Full day school. While class XI IPA 2 uses the usual learning approach. In learning in this science class, there are several stages carried out by researchers in learning. This research can provide insight into how changes in school schedules can affect.

So it can be concluded, based on the results of the trial above, it can be convincingly said that Full day school learning has shown a real influence, in the sense that it can be used as a good learning system in learning activities in class XI IPA MA MA AL-Khairiyah NW Rajek. The effect is shown from the results of hypothesis testing where it is known that the value of the significance level is $0.023 < 0.05$, meaning that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. It can also be seen from the comparison of r count with r table, namely $2,497 > 0.444$, which means H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. Which means that there is a significant influence on the application of Full day school on learning motivation. Then, based on the results of the data processing above, the Mean Different value is 9,600, the value is positive, meaning that the effect is positive.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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